

MODELING THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE CONSOLIDATION

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ABSTRACT

A model was developed which relates the processing cycle to the degree of intimate contact of the ply interfaces during consolidation of a thermoplastic composite. The model was developed by integrating a prepreg surface topology characterization with a resin flow analysis. Experiments were performed to obtain data to verify the model. Two-ply unidirectional laminae fabricated from graphite-polysulfone and graphite-PEEK prepregs were consolidated using different processing cycles. Agreement between the measured and calculated degree of intimate contact was good.

Keywords: composite processing, thermoplastic, prepreg, manufacturing.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, considerable attention has been focused on the use of tough, high-temperature, solvent-resistant thermoplastic polymers as matrix materials for fiber-reinforced composites. Thermoplastic resin systems have shown potential for reducing manufacturing costs and improving the damage tolerance of composite structures. In order to produce high-quality composite laminates from continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic prepregs and towpregs, the processing temperature and pressure must be selected so that intimate contact (coalescence) at the ply interfaces is achieved resulting in the formation of strong interply bonds (consolidation).

The mechanism by which a thermoplastic matrix composite consolidates to form a laminate has been identified as autohesive bond formation between plies [1]. However, autohesion can occur only after the plies coalesce (i.e. are physically in intimate contact). In fact previous investigations have shown that the time required for the ply interfaces to achieve intimate contact dominates the composite consolidation process. At typical consolidation temperatures, autohesive bonding occurs almost instantaneously.

During processing, specific combinations of pressure, temperature, and time result in varying degrees of intimate contact of the laminate ply interfaces. The objectives of this investigation were to develop a model which relates the processing cycle to the degree of intimate contact of the ply interfaces and to develop experimental techniques which can be used to measure the degree of intimate contact.

Loos and Dara [2] developed an intimate contact model for composite laminates fabricated from graphite-polysulfone prepreg. The prepreg tow heights were measured with a micrometer across a 304.8 mm (12 in) wide prepreg sheet, perpendicular to the fibers. The tow height distribution was fit to a two parameter Weibull function.

The resin impregnated fiber tows were treated as a homogenous fluid and deformation of the tows was modeled as a viscometric shear-thinning flow in the direction transverse to the fibers. The resin viscosity data were fit by the power-law model and the viscosity of the fiber/resin mixture was obtained by multiplying the neat resin viscosity by a reinforcement/viscosity influence factor c .

The degree of intimate contact was measured using the ultrasonic C-scan technique on $[0,90,0]_T$ composite laminates fabricated from graphite-polysulfone prepreg and compression molded using different processing cycles. The calculated degree of intimate contact was fit to the measured degree of intimate contact data by varying the power law parameters m and n and the reinforcement/viscosity influence factor c .

Lee and Springer [3] followed the approach of Loos and Dara [2] and developed a simplified intimate contact model for APC-2 graphite-PEEK prepreg. The tow height variation of the prepreg was described by a series of uniform rectangular elements. The deformation of the prepreg tows was modeled as a fully developed laminar flow of the fiber/matrix mixture. The viscosity of the fiber/matrix mixture was obtained by matching the results of the model to the intimate contact versus time data. The viscosity versus temperature relationship was described by an Arrhenius type equation.

In the verification of their model, Lee and Springer used only one ply of APC-2 prepreg. A single prepreg ply was compressed in a mold using different temperature, pressure and time conditions. After processing, the prepreg ply was removed from the mold and the compressed area was measured. The degree of intimate contact was determined by taking the ratio of the compressed area to the total area. The model matched the data well.

Mantel and Springer [4] modified the model developed by Lee and Springer [3] to simulate the manufacturing of thermoplastic composites by tape laying, filament winding and compression molding. Mantel et al. [5] experimentally verified the modified model using APC-2 prepreg. The ultrasonic C-scan technique was used to measure the degrees of intimate contact in 16-ply unidirectional short beam shear specimens and 2-ply lap shear specimens. The degree of intimate contact was determined by measuring the ply interfacial area in contact. The model was then matched with the data by varying two prepreg geometric parameters. The model fit the data with good accuracy.

As can be seen, the intimate contact models that have been developed require experimentally fitted parameters for solution of the governing equations. Loos and Dara [2] adjusted the power law and the reinforcement/viscosity model parameters to match the data. Likewise, Lee and Springer [3] varied the fiber/matrix mixture viscosity to fit the data and Mantel et al. [5] matched the experimental data with the prepreg geometric parameters. A goal of this investigation was to develop a new experimental technique which can be used to characterize the prepreg surface roughness and eliminate the empirical constants required for solution of the intimate contact model.

2. INTIMATE CONTACT MODEL

The uniformity of the prepreg microstructure and surface roughness are the critical parameters which govern selection of the processing pressure and time during consolidation. Figure 1 shows a photomicrograph of two prepreg plies during consolidation. A reasonable model of the prepreg is to assume that the prepreg consists of a fiber and resin core, possibly containing intraply voids, with resin rich surfaces. Spatial gaps due to prepreg surface roughness are eliminated during processing by localized deformation and flow at the resin rich surfaces. A model of this phenomenon was developed by integrating a prepreg surface topology characterization with a resin flow analysis. A formulation which uses the neat resin rheology was derived to describe the

deformation of the prepreg interply interface.

2.1 Prepreg Surface Characterization

The waviness or roughness of the resin rich prepreg ply surfaces were measured using a Talysurf 4 surface topology characterization machine. The measurements were taken across a 304.8 mm (12 in) wide prepreg sheet, perpendicular to the fibers. A typical result of the measurement is shown in Figure 2. The measurements are magnified by 20 X in the transverse fiber direction (2-direction) and by 500 X in the out-of-plane direction (3-direction). From the topology measurements it appears that the surface waviness (roughness) of the prepreg is somewhat sinusoidal. For modeling purposes the prepreg surface topology was represented by a series of rectangular elements of height h_0 , width b_0 and spacing w_0 , as shown in Figure 3. The magnitudes of b_0 and w_0 are equal. The results of the prepreg surface characterization for two types of prepreg are shown in Table 1. From Table 1, we can see that the T300/P1700 (T300 graphite fiber, Udel P1700 polysulfone resin) prepreg has a rougher surface than the APC-2 (AS4 graphite fiber, PEEK resin) prepreg. The conclusion was supported by the optical photomicrographs of the prepreg cross-section.

Table 1. Prepreg surface characterization results.

	Height (h_0) (mm) Average \pm Standard Deviation	Width and Spacing (b_0, w_0) Average \pm Standard Deviation
T300/P1700	0.05927 \pm 0.02245	2.311 \pm 0.655
APC-2	0.01263 \pm 0.01084	1.3034 \pm 0.8125

2.2 Flow Mechanics

In this investigation we follow the approach of Lee and Springer [3] and model the prepreg surface roughness by a series of uniform rectangular elements as shown in Figure 4. At the beginning of the consolidation process (time, $t = 0$), the initial height, width and spacing of the rectangular elements are given by the dimensions h_0 , b_0 and w_0 , respectively. Application of the consolidation pressure results in deformation of the rectangular elements which represents deformation and flow of the resin rich prepreg surfaces (Figure 4). Deformation and flow continues until the width of the elements are equal to the sum of the initial width and spacing of the elements. At this point the surfaces are in intimate contact.

Hence, the degree of intimate contact can be defined as [3]:

$$Dic = \frac{b}{w_0 + b_0} \quad (1)$$

where b is the instantaneous width of the rectangular elements at the time t . The deformation and flow of the rectangular elements can be modeled as a squeezing flow between two rigid parallel plates which are of infinite length in the x direction. Assuming that the resin viscosity is independent of shear rate, an expression for the degree of intimate contact can be written as [3]:

$$Dic = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{w_0}{b_0}} \left[1 + \frac{5P_{app}}{\eta_0} \left(1 + \frac{w_0}{b_0} \right) \left(\frac{h_0}{b_0} \right)^2 t \right]^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{app} is the nominal applied consolidation pressure and η_0 is the zero-shear-rate viscosity of the resin which is a function of processing temperature. For a specified applied pressure P_{app} , Equation 2 can be used to calculate the degree of intimate contact as a function of time. Equation

2 represents an expression for the degree of intimate contact of a single ply of prepreg in contact with a smooth rigid surface (Figure 4). If the initial element width and spacing are equal, Equation 2 can be simplified to:

$$Dic = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{10P_{app}}{\eta_0} \left(\frac{h_0}{b_0} \right)^2 t \right]^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (3)$$

A schematic representation of two prepreg plies in contact at the beginning of consolidation is shown in Figure 5. For this case it is assumed that there is no nesting of the ply surfaces and that adjacent plies are aligned to produce the largest spatial gaps. The rectangular elements of the lower ply will be aligned with the rectangular elements of the upper ply. Therefore, the initial element height becomes $2h_0$, and Equation 3 becomes:

$$Dic = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{10P_{app}}{\eta_0} \left(\frac{2h_0}{b_0} \right)^2 t \right]^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (4)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The model was used to calculate the degree of intimate contact versus time for both single-ply and two-ply prepreg samples. Comparisons between the results of the model and data reported by Lee and Springer [3] for single-ply APC-2 prepreg samples are shown in Figure 6. The surface characterization parameters for APC-2 prepreg in Table 1 and the zero-shear-rate viscosity for PEEK resin at the processing temperature were input into the intimate contact model for a single prepreg ply (Equation 2). As can be seen in the figure, the calculated degree of intimate contact agrees well with the measured degree of intimate contact for prepreg consolidated at different temperatures and pressures.

Two-ply graphite-polysulfone and graphite-PEEK prepreg specimens were compression molded using different processing cycles. After processing, the ply interfacial contact area (degree of intimate contact) was measured using optical microscopy. The results of the intimate contact model are compared with the experimental data in Figure 7 for T300/P1700 prepreg and in Figure 8 for APC-2 prepreg. For both types of prepreg, there is good agreement between the calculated and measured degree of intimate contact. The higher standard deviations in the measurements of h_0 , b_0 and w_0 for APC-2 prepreg (Table 1) might explain the higher data scatter in Figure 8. The data for both types of prepreg show that after long contact times, the maximum degree of intimate contact that can be achieved is about 95%. This may be due to voids that were trapped in the interply interface. The voids will appear as regions of incomplete contact in the photomicrographs. It is possible that higher consolidation pressures are required to collapse the entrapped voids.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

An analytical model was developed to predict the degree of intimate contact at the interply interfaces during consolidation of thermoplastic composites. Localized deformation and flow of the ply interface was modeled as a fully developed, laminar, squeezing flow. Input into the model includes the prepreg surface roughness parameters and the zero-shear-rate viscosity of the neat resin. The degree of intimate contact calculated using the model compares favorably with the degree of intimate contact measured during consolidation of unidirectional amorphous and semi-crystalline thermoplastic prepreps. In future work, the model will be extended to predict the degree of intimate contact at the ply interfaces of a thermoplastic composite with an arbitrary ply stacking sequence.

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REFERENCE

1. Voyutskii, S. S., *Autohesion and Adhesion of High Polymers*, Vol. 4, *Polymer Reviews*, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1963.
2. Loos, A. C. and Dara, P. H., "Processing of Thermoplastic Matrix Composites", *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, D. O. Thompson and D. E. Chimenti, Eds., Plenum Press, New York, 1987, Vol. 6B, pp.1257-1265.
3. Lee, W. I. and Springer, G. S., "A Model for the Manufacturing Process of Thermoplastic Matrix Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, November 1987, pp.1017-1055.
4. Mantel, S. C. and Springer, G. S., "Manufacturing Process Models for Thermoplastic Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No.16, 1992, pp.2348-2377.
5. Mantel, S. C., Wang, Q. and Springer, G. S., "Processing Thermoplastic Composites in a Press and by Tape Laying - Experimental Results", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No.16, 1992, pp.2378-2401.

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of two prepreg plies during consolidation.

Figure 2: A typical result of Talysurf 4 measurement on T300/P1700 prepreg.

Figure 3: Prepreg surface roughness modeling. A and P are the amplitude and the period of the sinusoidal wave.

Figure 4: Deformation of the rectangular elements against a rigid flat surface.

Figure 5: A schematic representation showing two prepreg plies in contact at the beginning of consolidation.

Figure 6: Degree of intimate contact versus time for single-ply APC-2 samples.

Figure 7: Degree of intimate contact versus time for two-ply T300/P1700 samples.

Figure 8: Degree of intimate contact versus time for two-ply APC-2 samples.

ENVIRONMENT

